

Quantum Interference from Zitterbewegung?

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In earlier notes, Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ has been converted into a linear 2x2 matrix equation (linear in E). The eigenvector $(\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v})$ found is related to forward and backward motion as a particle moves with an overall velocity v in the forward direction. It has been shown that this equation leads to the Schrodinger zitterbewegung of the Dirac equation and that even setting $v=0$ yields zitterbewegung in the remaining energy matrix.

In this note, we consider a particle moving backwards and forwards in a box with velocity v. In such a case, one needs two linear matrix equations, one for the forward motion and one for the backward. Similarly, one obtains two Schrodinger zitterbewegung results which on average cancel in some places. It is suggested that this cancellation may be related to quantum interference. As a check, the system of a particle bouncing backwards and forwards in a box can be thought of as a new particle with a mass M. Such a particle should itself satisfy the momentum energy equation if it is moving, say with velocity w, and one could apply the 2x2 matrix approach to it. There would be a new zitterbewegung and also a zitterbewegung for $w=0$. The zitterbewegung for $w=0$ should match that of the average of the zitterbewegungs for the particle moving to the right and to the left. We find that it has the same form, but not the same coefficients. For the average of the zitterbewegungs, there are coefficients depending on m/E while for the M approach, the coefficients are 1. A coefficient proportional to m/E suggests that for small m relative to p, there are very small zitterbewegung effects for this combined approach. In realistic systems with $v= 10^7$ m/s or so as in some quantum systems, m/E will be close to one and the two approaches will have almost the same coefficients. In classical mechanics, one may have a particle bounce back and forth in a box and can also consider the box to be a new system with a new mass, but there is no "cancellation" occurring.

2x2 Matrix Model

Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ can be written as a 2x2 matrix equation which has quantum mechanical properties. (see [1-9]), namely:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p & m \\ m & -p \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix} = E \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

One can see that a velocity matrix $V = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

yields an expectation value of "v" for the average velocity in one direction. The eigenvector $1/\sqrt{2} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1+v} \\ \sqrt{1-v} \end{pmatrix}$ leads to probabilities of $.5(1+v)$ for the particle to move to the right

and $.5(1-v)$ for it to move to the left as it moves with an average v to the right. Knuth [11] has also discussed similar behaviour. It is also possible to see that Schrodinger [1] zitterbewegung identical to that of the Dirac equation can be obtained from (1) namely:

$V(t) = \exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt)$ where H is the energy matrix in (1) and V the velocity matrix. Then:

$$V(t) = \cos^2(Et) V + i 2m \sin(Et)\cos(Et) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + (1/E^2) \sin^2(Et) \begin{bmatrix} p^2 - m^2 & 2pm \\ 2pm & m^2 - p^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.5)$$

Interestingly, the matrix $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ is proportional to dV/dt which is obtained from $[H, V]$.

It is also interesting to note that the 2x2 matrix model holds for $v=0$. In such a case, the velocity matrix remains the same, but (1) becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & m \\ m & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} |1\rangle \\ |1\rangle \end{bmatrix} = m \begin{bmatrix} |1\rangle \\ |1\rangle \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

It is interesting to note that the eigenvectors of the velocity matrix are $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ (forward and backward motion) and so the eigenstate in (2) is a combination of forward and backward motion with an average velocity of 0 i.e.

$$(1,1) \begin{bmatrix} |1 & 0\rangle \\ |0 & -1\rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} |1\rangle \\ |1\rangle \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

One can also obtain zitterbewegung for V from the energy matrix in (2) namely:

$$V(t) = \exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt) =$$

$$\cos^2(mt) V + i \sin(mt)\cos(mt) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \sin^2(mt) \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

This can be rewritten as:

$$V(t) = V + i \sin(mt)\cos(mt) 2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} - 2 \sin^2(mt) V \quad (2.75)$$

Case of a Particle Moving Forwards and Backwards in a Box

Let us consider the case of a particle moving forwards and backwards in a box. In such a case, it would have an average velocity v moving forward and $-v$ moving backwards. Thus, (1) would

hold for the forward case, but one would have to replace v with $-v$ and p with $-p$ in (1) to obtain an equation for the backward motion. Similarly, the zitterbewegung of (2.5) would hold for forward motion and (2.5) with v and p replaced with $-v$ and $-p$ for backward motion. One can see that the term in (2.5) with p^2-m^2 do not change under a sign change while $2mp$ does so it appears that there is "interference" and the $2mp$ terms in matrices drop. The overall average zitterbewegung operator becomes:

$$V(t) = \cos^2(Et) V + i 2(m/E) \sin(Et)\cos(Et) \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} + (1/E^2) \sin^2(Et) \begin{vmatrix} p^2-m^2 & 0 \\ 0 & m^2-p^2 \end{vmatrix} \quad (3)$$

This can be rewritten as:

$$V(t) = V + i 2(m/E) \sin(Et)\cos(Et) \begin{vmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} - (2m^2/E^2) \sin^2(Et) V \quad (3.5)$$

Now, it should be possible to consider this problem in a different way. Imagine that the particle bouncing back and forth in the box is a new system with an overall energy equal to a rest mass M . Then $M = \sqrt{p^2 + m^2} = E$. Imagine that there is an observer moving with a speed $-w$. This observer will see a system with $(E/w)^2 = P^2 + M^2$. This new system can again be analyzed using the 2x2 matrix approach and will have zitterbewegung as will the new M . In terms of the original v, m and p on has:

$$B \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -v \\ |p| & |E| \end{vmatrix} = B \begin{vmatrix} |p-vE| & |vp+E| \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{where } B = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2}$$

$$\text{Thus, } B(vp+E) = M/\sqrt{1-w^2}$$

If one considers the zitterbewegung of this new system with $w=0$, then one has the result of (2.5) again. In such a case, the energy eigenvector is $(1,1)$. In terms of the original system of the bouncing particle, the forward and backward bouncing eigenvectors of (1) and (1) with p and v replaced with $-v$ are: $(\sqrt{1+v}, \sqrt{1-v}) + (\sqrt{1-v}, \sqrt{1+v})$ which is proportional to $(1,1)$. For $w=0$ terms such as $\sin(mt)$ appear in (2.75), but now m is replaced with M which is equivalent to E for the p, v, m particle.

One sees that the zitterbewegung with interference (3.5) matches the zitterbewegung of the new system with $w=0$ namely (2.75) with the exception that coefficients on the zitterbewegung terms are different. For the $w=0$ case (2.75) the coefficients are 2 and -2 while for the average of the bouncing particle they are $2(m/E)$ and $-2(m^2/E^2)$. It is possible to create the same $M=E$ by changing values of p and m . In the 2x2 matrix model for M , its zitterbewegung cannot know which p, m choice was made, so it cannot depend on p and m . For the average zitterbewegung of the bouncing particle, there is dependence on p and m in the form of m/E . It should be noted

that for $m \ll p$, there would be a tiny zitterbewegung effect for the bouncing particle. In many systems in nature, however, $m \gg p$. Let us imagine $E = m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ with $v = 10^7$ m/s. This would still lead to an E almost equal to m . In such a case, the coefficients of the two approaches are very much the same.

We suggest that this zitterbewegung with interference between the forward and backward moving particle may describe quantum interference as it leads to a different velocity distribution in time which is related to spatial density. Thus, there interference leading to a change in spatial density when a 2x2 matrix particle moving to the right interferes with itself (its zitterbewegung) when it is moving to the left. This interference seems to be a kind of average of the two zitterbewegungs. In classical physics, density is related to dx/v . Here things are not so simple. It should be noted that a 2x2 matrix particle is moving backwards and forwards while moving with an average speed v in one direction. Thus, the particle "exists" in a region of space (related to the wavelength). Thus, near a reflecting wall there is uncertainty as to whether one has components of the particle moving to the right or to the left. We use this as a possible justification for considering "interference" between the zitterbewegung of the particle and its reflected state $-v$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that if one considers the 2x2 matrix approach for a particle bouncing backwards and forwards in box, one obtains two different zitterbewegung expressions. Averaging these, leads to the cancellation of some terms suggesting that there might be "quantum interference" occurring. The average zitterbewegung result matches closely the zero velocity zitterbewegung result for a new particle (composed of the bouncing particle). Thus, we argue that interference features are related to zitterbewegung. We and others have argued that zitterbewegung is related to the wavelength and so a quantum particle (or 2x2 matrix particle) is not really localized and it seems that interference may be possible, even as part of an averaging process.

References

1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zitterbewegung>
2. Quantum Mechanical Formalism Contained in Special Relativity? (preprint), F. R. Ruggeri, Zenodo (2018).
3. Two Zitterbewegung Formalism? (preprint) Ruggeri, F. R., Zenodo (2018).
4. Problem with Schrodinger Zitterbewegung? (preprint) Ruggeri, F. R. Zenodo (2018)
5. A 2x2 Matrix Approach to the Relativistic Energy Momentum Equation Follows Naturally (preprint) Ruggeri, F. R., Zenodo (2018).

6. Quantum Mechanical Aspects In Classical Physics? (preprint)
Ruggeri, F.R. Zenodo (2018).
7. Spatial Aspects of a 2x2 Matrix Model of Einstein's Relativistic Momentum Energy Equation
And Applications to Light (preprint) Ruggeri, F.R. Zenodo (2018).
8. Dynamics of 2x2 Relativistic Matrix Model of Energy Momentum Equation (preprint)
Ruggeri, Francesco R., Zenodo 2018.
9. Roots of Zitterbewegung and the DeBroglie Wavelength in a 2x2 Matrix Approach to the Relativistic Momentum Energy Equation (preprint) Ruggeri, Francesco R. Zenodo 2018.
10. Hestenes, David. The Kinematic Origin of Complex Wavefunctions. U. of Cambridge Press
<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.455.276&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
11. Knuth, Kevin. The Problem of Motion: The Statistical Mechanics of Zitterbewegung. arXiv 2014